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ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS AND ENVIRONMENTAL VALUES

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ABSTRACT

The real wealth of any nation and any region lies in the wellbeing of its people. The three main problems in the world, are known as three-P-Population, Poverty, and Pollution. Pollution is the main problem of the modern world. The technological inventions and progress has over powered nature, it has also resulted in the thoughtless exploitation of nature. Awareness by educating everyone, to value the nature and maintain the natural environment are important need. A study was conducted a 50 private and govt. female school students to measure the environmental values. Environmental Value Test (Shrivastav & Dubey, 1995) was used to assess the environmental value of the sample age range varied from 16-17 yrs. Findings of the study reveal that there is degree of high environmental value among both urban groups. Eco-club, Vanmahotsava, Exhibitions are popular means of creating awareness about environment. The need of the hour is to discuss environmental issues as our environmental issues, at global level as a sense of duty. To protect the environment from the adverse effects of pollution, many nations worldwide have enacted legislation to regulate various types of pollution to mitigate their harmful effects.

Keywords:

Environmental Value Test, environmental issues, environmental issues.

INTRODUCTION

Human depends on the environment for its everyday needs right from the days begins till it ends. Environment is defined as the sum total aggregate of all the conditions, forces and influences man made and nature. Human beings are both the agents and victims of environment changes. Values refer to the beliefs of specific kind of thinking.. UNESCO has related values with nature. It includes love for plants, vegetable, trees, animal kingdom, rivers, jungles, mountains etc. Environmental attitude is learned predisposition to respond towards a consistently given object negative or positive. Environmental behaviour determines those actions which contribute towards environmental preservation and conservation is more eco-friendly awareness. Environment Pollution is the inferable change of the surroundings due to direct or indirect effects of changes in energy patterns, radiation levels, chemical and physical change. Tap problems of environmental quality today include deforestation. Global warming, biodiversity loss, and hazardous waste. Waste Awareness and Management is need among citizens, authorities, industrialists, entrepreneurs. The major objective of the study was to measure the environmental values of Govt. and Private urban school female students. It was hypothesized that, “there will be no significant difference in environmental values of private and government school students.”

METHODS

The present study was conducted on female students of class XI. 25 girls from St. J.C.S.S. School and 25 girls from Govt. M.L.B. School were participated. The sample selection was purposive. The objective of the study was explained to them. Environmental Value Test developed by Dr. Shrivastav and Dr. Dubey 1995, was used to collect the data. High Score on the scale indicates high and very high degree of value.

SAMPLE

School	N	Class	Mean	S.D.	t-test
Govt. M.L.B. School	25	XI	55.20	20.90	0.73
Private St. J.C.S.S.	25	XI	58.80	20.90	

Degrees of freedom – 48

Minimum Value of
0.05 level = 2.01
0.01 level = 2.68

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To verify the hypothesis t-test was calculated. Obtained value of t-test is 0.73 which is less than the minimum value for significance at 0.05 level as such there is no significant difference in environmental values between two urban groups. It can be inferred from the above result that there is no difference in environmental values of govt. and private school students. Hypothesis is accepted here. Mean value indicated that private school students are having high and very high degree of environmental value than govt. school.

Results reveal that students are having enough awareness and skills, for identifying and solving problems. Researchers found that higher rate of mental illness in poor environment while mentally healthy people are being found in the rich environment. Other studies reveal that people living in the places surrounded with trees have pleasant personality characteristics. People living in barren land are found more frustrated and aggressive (Goranso and King 1970), Cognitive overlap such as hustle and bustle of the city, bright lights on roads and in shops, vehicle sound, smoking, perfumes, dirty habits of people cause pollution in the environment. The present education system should teach the youngsters to value the nature and importance of natural environment. The Sanskrit literature has reported the values of nature. Beauty of hills, mountains, snowclade peeks, rivers, streams, takes, trees, plants, flowers, animals, rocks, jungles, etc. are not only things to admire, but they form the life and soul of humanity. Bhumi-Universal mother is the basis of life. Importance of various trees, plants, flowers, birds and wild life for humanity and survival of the mankind is indescribable. The idea of worshiping of trees is to plant and preserve them. Vanaspati is used in Suktas serve as medicine. Hence they should be planted regularly. A good number of plants and trees are associated with god and goddess. Animals and birds are also co-related with god and goddess. It is only to respect and keep safe and secure these creatures. In the same way rivers are considered as goddess or daughters of gods in order to keep them clean and pious. Mountains and hills are worshiped. It is only to make people aware and respect the nature. The immediate steps required for the environmental management are environmental education, environmental legislation and its implementation, monitoring and mapping of environment.

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